

EFFECT OF EXCHANGE RATE VOLATILITY ON NIGERIA'S FINANCIAL INCLUSION

¹Adedayo Olawale Clement (Ph.D.), ^{2*}Akinuli Bankole Olu (Ph.D.), ³Popoola Olukemi Elizabeth (Ph.D.) and ⁴Remi-Esan Sumbo Sherifat M.Sc.

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Abstract

This study assessed the effect of exchange rate volatility on financial inclusion in Nigeria from 2009 to 2023 using the Arch and Garch technique for volatility measurement. The study employed three models to level up financial inclusion: number of point of sale (POS), value of automated teller machine transactions, and financial knowledge. The results from the study showed that exchange rate volatility exerts a negative effect on financial inclusion through the number of points of sale (POS), while financial knowledge has a positive effect with exchange rate volatility. The findings also revealed that through higher lending rates, exchange rate volatility yields a negative effect on the financial market. The paper recommended that the value of the country currency should be enhanced to improve the efficiency and depth of the financial sector. This can be achieved by increasing local productivity. In addition, policymakers in Nigeria should work at ensuring a low and stable inflation rate to prevent hampering financial inclusion and efficiency in Nigeria.

1.1 Introduction

The concept of financial inclusion is becoming increasingly popular in the literature, especially in developing countries in Asia and Africa, due to its role in determining the course of economic growth and development. In the early 2000s, financial inclusion became popular in a bid to find a solution to the problem of poverty and economic growth resulting from the adverse effects of financial exclusion (Atta & Ibrahim, 2024). Financial inclusion refers to the availability and accessibility of financial services to all individuals and businesses. Singh and Singh Kondan (2011) defined financial inclusion as the process of ensuring that individuals and businesses in a particular community have access to affordable and sustainable formal financial services and products, such as savings, payments, credit cards, insurance, and other transactions. Financial inclusion is concerned with

^{1,3,4}Students, Department of Finance, Adekunle Ajasin University, Akungba-Akoko, Nigeria

²Candidate, Finance Department, University of Benin, Benin-City, Edo-State, Nigeria

providing affordable, adequate, and access to formal financial services to the poor and underserved individuals and businesses in society (Sarma & Pais, 2011). Financial inclusion extends beyond access and use of financial services, including access to quality financial services. This means that quality financial services should be timely, safe, user-friendly, and responsive to customer needs (Tissaoui et al., 2024).

In developing countries, a significant proportion of the population is poor and vulnerable, and they are spread across communities where they have no access to basic financial services, such as making and receiving payments (Demirgüç-Kunt, et al., 2020). Being financially included begins with having a deposit account with a bank or other non-banking financial institution or through a mobile money service provider where money can be received and payment made using some of the financial innovative channels, such as the ATM, POS, banking apps, and USSD codes, among others, that facilitate access and usage of financial services in underserved communities. Access to credit facilities from formal financial institutions is another crucial aspect of financial inclusion. Access to and usage of insurance products will enable individuals and businesses to effectively manage their risks.

Financial inclusion is seen as a potent tool or strategy for development or poverty eradication and increased shared prosperity (Atta & Ibrahim, 2024). Financial inclusion reduces the dominance of the informal sector, which could hinder the effectiveness of a country's monetary policy (Garcia, 2016). Morgan and Pontines (2018) argued that financial inclusion has the potential to bring about extensive and efficient savings mobilization while engendering a more stable base of retail deposits.

In Nigeria, those who have access to the financial system have many difficulties to overcome to enjoy the services. Individuals and business groups still face difficulties such as documentation, high transaction costs, and nearness to bank branches, among others (Beck et al., 2007).

The nexus between foreign exchange volatility has not been adequately explored. Vo (2019) found a negative relationship between financial inclusion and macroeconomic stability, either by increasing the level of financial risks or decreasing macroeconomic stability. Volatility in foreign exchange can impact financial inclusion in several ways. For instance, a volatile exchange rate can make it difficult for individuals and businesses to manage their financial risks, particularly those involved in international trade or with foreign currency-denominated assets or liabilities. Furthermore, foreign exchange fluctuations can affect borrowers' creditworthiness, especially those with foreign currency-denominated loans, as this can limit access to credit for some individuals and businesses. Exchange rate fluctuations can affect remittances and investment. The value of remittances received by individuals reduces, while investments, particularly foreign investment, which is an important factor for economic growth and financial inclusion, are deterred.

Exchange rate fluctuations can also make the financial market more complex, requiring higher levels of financial literacy to navigate, which may result in the exclusion of people with lower financial literacy. Similarly, exchange rate volatility can lead to inflation, which disproportionately affects the financially excluded, who may hold cash assets or have limited access to hedging instruments.

A plethora of studies have been conducted since the concept of financial inclusion emerged in the 2000s. However, the majority of studies focused on financial inclusion and growth and development rather than investigating the effects of financial inclusion's exchange rate volatility. For instance, Cicchiello et al. (2021) studied the effect of financial inclusion on development in the least developed countries in Asia and Africa. Chuka et al. (2022) conducted a study on financial inclusion and its impact on economic growth in Sub-Saharan Africa. Meanwhile, each country has variations in macroeconomic variables that influence financial inclusion, limiting its potential for economic growth and development.

In this study, the effects of exchange rate volatility on various dimensions of financial inclusion, such as access, usage, and quality of financial services, were investigated to ascertain the potential of financial inclusion for

Nigeria's growth and development. This study provides empirical evidence to fill the research gap and provides insight into the link between foreign exchange volatility and financial inclusion in Nigeria.

Literature Review

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Financial inclusion

Financial inclusion refers to the process by which individuals and businesses can access and use affordable financial services (Vo et al., 2019). Singh and Singh Kondan (2011) defined financial inclusion as the process of ensuring that individuals, households, and businesses in a community have unhindered access to formal financial services products, such as transactions, savings, payments, credit cards, insurance, and their delivery in a sustainable manner.

Financial inclusion is the opposite of financial exclusion, i.e., lack of access to financial services (Marshall, 2004; Wilson, 2012; Buckland, 2012). Demigüç-kunt et al. (2011) affirmed that a large number of poor and vulnerable individuals, households, groups, and communities in developing countries are denied access to basic formal financial services, such as bank accounts, payment services, and remittance payments or receipts. Mckinsey Explainers (2023) opines that financial inclusion is a major issue around the globe as an estimated 1.5 billion people in developing economies do not have access to formal savings and credit. Okoduwa and Odiboh (2023) described financial exclusion as both a symptom and a cause of poverty. As of 2020, an estimated 35.97 percent of the Nigerian population is still financially excluded, lacking access to formal financial services as at 2020.

The focus of financial inclusion is to widen the country's financial network and create an efficient delivery of financial services. Financial inclusion entails making financial services, such as savings and deposit accounts, loans, payment services, and micro insurance services, accessible to both individuals and small businesses at an affordable cost.

Sahay et al. (2015) see all the functions of financial inclusion as a way of improving the people's personal well-being while also reducing poverty and enhancing the economy's growth and development. This is due to its efficacy in strengthening economic empowerment and enabling active participation in the financial system by the youth, women, and other vulnerable groups that are financially excluded in the community (Hendriks, 2019; Siddik, 2017). A well-developed financial system can facilitate economic growth as it serves as a means through which investment can be attracted for the overall development of the country. In addition, where there is development, the development will engender a broadening of financial services and the financial system as a whole (Cicchello, 2021).

2.1.2 Volatility of Exchange Rates

According to Mordi (2006), exchange rate volatility refers to fluctuations in exchange rates over a period of time. The exchange rate of a country is the nominal exchange rate and is usually published by the country's monetary authority. Adjusting the nominal exchange rate used in calculating the relative price level between two countries determines the real exchange rate.

Exchange rate fluctuations influence the daily or weekly transaction costs, diminishing the economic growth process whenever the unpredictability is high and hedging foreign exchange risk is high-priced (Ali, 2022). When the exchange rate is stable, as witnessed during the process of European monetary integration, efficiency, productivity, and comfort will increase (European Commission, 1990). Morina et al. (2020) stated that foreign exchange is an essential macroeconomic factor that influences foreign trade and the real economy of an individual nation. The volatility of a country's exchange rate exerts a direct influence on imports and export activities, the structure of production, and the economic setting. A reduction in the ratios of local currency to foreign currency will facilitate.

Exchange rate volatility is the continuous fluctuations of the exchange rate. The volatility of exchange rate has become a popular topic of discussion in recent times as it affects the economies of developing countries. Wang and Barret (2007) and Arinze et al. (2000) affirmed that exchange rate fluctuations have become surprisingly popular in both developed and developing nations due to the influence it exerts on importation.

In Nigeria, the floatation of the naira in 2023 allows it to be determined by the market forces of demand and supply with the view of unifying the official exchange rate and parallel exchange rate, putting the country on a trajectory of growth and development by stimulating investment and trade has brought about a higher rate of fluctuations in the exchange rate reducing the value of naira against major currencies like the US Dollar, British Pounds Sterling, Euro, among others, thereby impacting the inflation rate and by extension financial inclusion.

Excessive exchange rate volatility is counterproductive for the real economy. The level or threshold at which the exchange rate volatility begins to negatively impact the real economy depends on the size of the economies. Small economies are more negatively impacted than large economies when the exchange rate is above the threshold. Furthermore, higher exchange rate volatility cannot guarantee financial market development (Mohanty, 2013). This position aligned with the arguments of McKinnon (1963) that when a country adopts a fixed exchange rate regime, it benefits from price stability, especially when the country relies heavily on imported goods for both consumption and production, as in the case of Nigeria. Furthermore, the fixed exchange regime facilitates investment, increasing trade and output growth due to the reduction in transaction and other risk-mitigating costs brought about by a reduced exchange rate uncertainty level (Frankel & Rose, 2002).

2.2 Theoretical Review

2.2.1 Risk management theory

Risk management theory is rooted in various disciplines, such as economics, finance, and management. While it is difficult to attribute the theory to a single proponent, notable contributors to the theory include economic theorists such as Frank Knight (1921) and John Maynard Keynes (1921) and financial theorists such as Harry Markowitz (1952) and William Sharpe (1964).

The theory posited that individuals, businesses, and organizations make decisions based on their risk tolerance and perceived likelihood of potential losses or gain. Risk management theory that foreign exchange volatility increases uncertainty and risk in the context of foreign exchange volatility. Risk-averse individuals and businesses reduce their exposure to foreign exchange transactions while financial institutions adjust their lending and investment strategies to mitigate potential losses. In relation to the concept of financial inclusion, foreign exchange volatility increases risk, causing financial institutions to reduce their lending and investment in vulnerable sectors, resulting in financial exclusion. Risk edging as a strategy for risk management will also increase transaction costs, thereby making financial services less accessible to the underserved or marginalized groups in society. Volatility in foreign exchange can also cause complications in financial decision-making, reducing literacy among people and businesses.

2.3 Empirical Review

There is a plethora of literature on financial inclusion and foreign exchange volatility in different contexts, times, and locations, even though few studies discuss the nexus between foreign exchange volatility and financial inclusion. For instance, Vo et al. (2019) examined the relationship between financial inclusion and macroeconomic stability in emerging and frontier markets between 2008 and 2015 using panel threshold-estimated techniques to analyze the effect of Bank Z-score, NPL, inflation volatility, and exchange rate volatility on output growth. They found that financial inclusion facilitates financial stability under a certain threshold, while it brings about stability of inflation and output growth. Although the study established a link between financial inclusion and macroeconomic stability in emerging and frontier economies, it does not

explain the link between exchange rate volatility and financial inclusion, particularly for Nigeria, where the issue of exchange rate volatility as it affects financial inclusion is of importance.

In their study, Cicchiello et al. (2021) attempted to establish the effects of financial inclusion on development in the least developed countries in Asia and Africa. They adopted annual data on the Financial Inclusion Index, Gross Domestic Product (GDP), total rural population, unemployment rate, literacy rate of women, and income inequality (Gini coefficient) from 42 countries between 2000 and 2019 and subjected the data to pooled panel regression analysis techniques. The results revealed that economic growth facilitates financial inclusion. Unemployment and literacy rates are among the factors contributing to financial inclusion. Furthermore, women are more vulnerable than men to lack financial inclusion. While it concluded that in less developed countries, the economies rely on agriculture and the people are less financially inclusive when they live in the rural areas of the countries, income inequality reduces financial inclusion rates, which has a negative impact on development by reducing the level of development, the study did not consider the role of foreign exchange fluctuations in determining financial inclusion in the countries under consideration.

Chuka et al. (2022) studied the impact of financial inclusion on economic growth in Sub-Saharan Africa. They adopted General method moments (GMM) to analyze data from 22 Sub-Saharan African countries between 2012 and 2018. They found that the composite financial inclusion index and individual financial inclusion indicators in its various dimensions exert significant and positive effects on economic growth. As indicated in the results, the usage dimension of financial inclusion has a positive but insignificant impact on economic growth. Bank branches and ATMs are positively and significantly related to economic growth, whereas deposit accounts and outstanding loans have a positive but non-significant effect on economic growth. Moreover, the findings revealed that mobile money agents weaken economic growth, whereas mobile money accounts and mobile money transactions facilitate economic growth in a non-significant manner. Even though the study examined financial inclusion in its various dimensions, it did not find its nexus with the region's prevailing foreign exchange rate volatility.

Persaud and Thaffe (2023) examined the state of research on financial inclusion in developing countries by reviewing 183 peer-reviewed journal articles extracted from Scopus. The study, which found a fragmented literature with mixed and contested evidence, was not Nigeria specific as it recommended that the social implications of financial inclusion should be examined within a specific institutional context while being careful in applying successful models from one context to the next.

Girón et al. (2022) examined the measurement of financial inclusion in the least developed countries in Asia and Africa by investigating financial inclusion (official accounts, formal savings, official credit—a dummy variable taking 1 if an individual has a formal account, formal; saving and official credit), gender, age, income, and education without considering foreign exchange fluctuations. The World Bank data set, which was subjected to probit econometric techniques, revealed financial exclusion among young people and women groups, while education and income are the two key elements or factors that facilitate financial inclusion. Also, an increase in the level of financial inclusion brings about an increase in official savings in countries, and hence, development. It was concluded that the level of financial inclusion is low in the least developed countries and that a higher level of financial inclusion will facilitate a higher level of economic growth and development. Similarly, Hussain et al. (2024) examined the relationship between financial inclusion and growth in 21 Asian countries by adopting data between 2004 and 2019 on GDP per capita, number of ATMs per 100,000 adults, number of bank branches per 100,000 adults, number of commercial banks, outstanding loans as a percentage of GDP, outstanding deposits as a percentage of GDP, trade openness, population, industry as a percentage of GDP, and mobile subscription per 100 persons. The results of the data set subjected to several pre-estimation tests and econometric tests, such as the Pesaran and Shin panel unit root test, cointegration test, CS-ARDL model, and Dumitrescu-Hurlin (D-H) panel causality approach indicated that there exist a significant positive

long-term effect of financial inclusion on economic growth in Asia. The findings also revealed a causality between financial inclusion and economic growth development. Boachie and Adu-Darko (2024) examined the effects of financial inclusion on economic growth in 47 Sub-Saharan African countries between 2010 and 2020 using GDP, labor force, stock of physical capital, stock of human capital, financial inclusion indicators, government expenditure, inflation, and trade openness with descriptive statistics and OLS as the analysis method. The results revealed a positive correlation between financial inclusion and economic growth using the Driscoll–Kay error estimate approach and concluded that financial inclusion exerts a beneficial effect on economic growth through human capital.

In their study to unravel the factors limiting financial inclusion and development in Peru, Nández Alonso et al. (2024) adopted data ranging from the number of ATMs per km², the number of ATMs per 100,000 adults, numbers of bank branches per km², and numbers of bank branches per 100,000 adults. Bar charts, graphs, maps, and analysis of variance (ANOVA) were used to analyze the data collected, which enabled comparison between Peru and other selected South American countries, such as Argentina, Chile, Colombia, Ecuador, Paraguay, Venezuela, Uruguay, Brazil, and Bolivia. The study found that areas in rural Peru, such as the inland, mountainous, or jungle regions, are posed with a higher risk of financial exclusion caused by a higher rate of digital illiteracy, inadequate usage of digital banking, scattered bank branches and ATM distributions, and a shortage of means of transportation. In their study, the authors only adopted two (access and usage) dimensions out of the three dimensions (access, usage, and quality) of financial inclusion, ignoring the quality dimension of the financial inclusion measurement in measuring its effects on development.

In Nigeria, Atta and Ibrahim (2024) examined the influence of financial inclusion on economic development in Nigeria and adopted the money supply, credit to the private sector, and loan-to-deposit ratio as a proxy for financial inclusion to explain the changes in GDP per capita. With the adoption of descriptive statistics, Unit root test, ARDL bound test, and ARDL cointegration to analyze data between 1981 and 2022, the result of the analysis showed that a short- and long-term relationship exists between financial inclusion and economic growth, which is in tandem with the finance growth theory adopted for the study. The study concluded that financial inclusion possesses the potential to drive wealth creation, reduce poverty, improve welfare, and achieve sustainable development. Although the study was conducted to establish the relationship between financial inclusion and economic development, the choice of variables, such as bank size, size, and financial depth of banking, adopted to proxy financial inclusion was not appropriate as it is more of financial deepening than inclusion. In a similar study earlier conducted by Obademi and Adeniran (2019) to examine the nexus between financial inclusion and economic growth in Nigeria, a survey was conducted with 220 questionnaires, and the data collected were subjected to simple linear regression to test the hypotheses. The results of the analysis indicated a significant relationship between local credit, financial inclusion, and commercial bank deposits and economic growth. The study concluded that financial inclusion affects growth within the period under review and that the central bank of Japan (CBN) should embark on a viable process to accelerate financial inclusion growth for prompt economic growth.

Esu et al. (2024) examined financial inclusion, economic growth, and macroeconomic stability in Nigeria between 1980 and 2022, adopting variables such as GDP growth rate, broad money-to-GDP (M2/GDP), credit-to-private sector (CPS/GDP), loan-to-deposit ratio, liquidity ratio, bank lending interest rate, foreign exchange rate, and inflation between 1980 and 2022. The study, which adopted the ARDL bound test, ARDL error correction, and ADF unit root test in its analysis, found that financial inclusion may not necessarily improve economic growth and may not foster economic stability in the short run. However, financial inclusion enhances the growth of the economy in the long run, but at a slow growth rate while stabilizing the macroeconomy (price level) in the long run. Although the foreign exchange rate was included in the variables, its relationship with financial inclusion was established in the study.

Bassey et al. (2015) examined the relationship between financial inclusion and banking system growth in Nigeria, focusing on microfinance, mobile payments, KYC, electronic payments, bank charges, non-interest banking, agent banking, financial literacy bank charges, consumer protection, implementation of MSME development funds, and credit enhancement programs. The review of the extant literature indicated that the various initiatives of the Central Bank of Nigeria aim to reach a large part of the financially excluded population in Nigeria and improve their welfare while ensuring that they are captured in the formal banking system. The study concluded that various impediments, such as illiteracy, low income, poverty, and inadequate bank branches in some rural communities without recourse to the prevailing exchange rate fluctuations, hinder financial inclusion in Nigeria. In another similar study, Nnaomah et al. (2024) compared digital banking and financial inclusion practices in the United States and Nigeria and conducted a review of the existing literature and analysis of case studies. The study results revealed that digital banking contributed significantly to the development of financial inclusion in Nigeria, while access to financial services brought about by digital banking in the USA was fostered by the country's technological advancement and the robust regulatory framework. In Nigeria, infrastructural and regulatory frameworks are still a great barrier to accessing financial services. The authors concluded that both countries are leveraging digital banking to promote financial inclusion but with variations in the mode of implementation and success resulting from the differential in regulatory framework, technologies, and economic development.

Inegbedion et al. (2022) investigated the effects of financial inclusion and entrepreneurship creation among agency banking operators in Lagos Metropolis, Nigeria. Financial index (banking penetration, availability and accessibility of services/products, usage of banking system/technology) and employment (entrepreneurship/job creation) were considered in the survey conducted on 399 POS operators in Lagos. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and regression analysis for hypothesis testing. The results revealed that banking penetration exerts a significant positive influence on entrepreneurship creation of services, with financial services and products having a significant positive relationship with entrepreneurship creation, while banking services usage exerts a significant and positive influence on entrepreneurship creation among POS operators in Lagos. The study concluded that POS operators and agent banks are useful in promoting financial inclusion and job creation. However, agency banking should expand financial incentives to POS and mobile banking operators to facilitate their access to funds. However, the study, which was restricted to Lagos Metropolis, should have been extended to POS operators in rural areas, as access to and usage of financial services in rural areas remain inadequate.

3.0 Methodology

3.1 Data collection and analysis

Exchange rate volatility can affect the access and use of formal financial services by households and firms. To quantify whether and how exchange rate volatility affects financial inclusion in Nigeria, the study adopted secondary data using time series data for a robust econometric analysis. Annual data from 2009 to 2023 on exchange rate volatility, inflation, lending interest rate, trade openness, and variables representing the three dimensions (access, usage, and quality) of financial inclusion, such as numbers of point of sale (POS), value of automated teller machine transactions, and financial knowledge, were collected from the Annual Statistical Bulletin of the Central Bank of Nigeria 2023 and the World Bank Financial Index Data Base 2023 to analyze the effects of foreign exchange volatility on financial inclusion in Nigeria. The study adopted Arch and Garch for the analysis after testing for unit root stationary of each variable to test the effects of exchange rate volatility on the number of bank branches, the value of POS transactions, and financial knowledge, which represent financial inclusion in each of the three models formulated for the study.

3.2 Model Specifications

Based on the empirical literature, three regression models were developed for this study to express the effects of foreign exchange volatility on the three dimensions of financial inclusion. The models were developed following Chuka et al. (2022). Burjorjee and Scola (2015) posited that the measure of financial inclusion in its dimensions includes access, use, and quality. Access is defined by physical proximity, affordability, and convenience; use is defined by financial capability, actual use, such as regularity, frequency, and length of time; and quality involves adaptation to client needs and provision of services in a responsible and sustainable manner. As a result, the number of bank branches, the value of POS transactions, and financial knowledge were adopted as the dependent variables in each of the three models. The independent variables included exchange rate volatility, inflation, lending interest rate, and trade openness, which were used in each model to establish changes in each dimension of financial inclusion.

The regression models are as follows:

Model One:

$$\text{NuBBranch} = \beta_0 + \beta_1\text{ExR} + \beta_2\text{InfR} + \beta_3\text{LndR} + \beta_4\text{TrdOp} + \mu$$

Dependent variable: Bank branches per 100,000 adults (BBranch)

Independent Variables: Exchange rate (ExR), inflation rate (InfR), lending rate (LndR), trade openness (TrdOp)

Model Two:

$$\text{ValPOSTran} = \beta_0 + \beta_1\text{ExR} + \beta_2\text{InfR} + \beta_3\text{LndR} + \beta_4\text{TrdOp} + \mu$$

Dependent variable: Value of the POS transaction (VPOSTrans)

Independent Variables: Exchange rate (ExR), inflation rate (InfR), lending rate (LndR), and trade openness (TrdOp)

Model Three:

$$\text{FinKnw} = \beta_0 + \beta_1\text{ExR} + \beta_2\text{InfR} + \beta_3\text{LndR} + \beta_4\text{TrdOp} + \mu$$

Dependent variable: Financial Knowledge Score (FinKnw)

Independent Variables: Exchange rate (ExR), inflation rate (InfR), lending rate (LndR), and trade openness (TrdOp)

Where;

β_0 is constant, β_1 , β_2 , β_3 , and β_4 are coefficients of the independent variables while μ is the error term. NuBBranch is the number of bank branches measuring access to financial services, ValPOSTran is the value of POS transactions measuring the usage of financial services in Nigeria, and FinKnw is the quality of financial knowledge. ExR is the exchange rate volatility, InfR is the inflation rate, LndR is the lending rate, and TrdOp (Ex-Im) is the trade openness.

3.3 A priori expectations

Based on the theoretical and empirical literature, this study expects that exchange rate volatility will exert a negative effect on Nigeria's financial inclusion. This is because high levels of exchange rate fluctuations tend to increase macroeconomic uncertainty, discourage investment, raise transaction costs, and weaken confidence in the financial system. This condition may reduce the willingness of households and firms to engage with formal financial institutions, lowering financial inclusion levels.

4.1 Results and Discussions

Table 1: Stationarity test results in summary and the order of integration

Variables	ADF test statistic value	5% Mackinnon critical value	Phillips-Perron test statistic value	5% Mackinnon critical value	Remark	Order of integration

EXR	-4.477872	-4.008154	-11.74420	-4.205004	Stationary	I(1)
LndR	-6.237267	-4.886426	-9.436176	-4.205004	Stationary	I(1)
InfR	-4.443101	-3.828975	-4.681898	-4.205004	Stationary	I(1)
TrdOp	-5.254923	-4.008157	-4.603676	-4.205004	Stationary	I(1)
NuBBranch	-3.551769	-4.046311	-4.321960	-4.205004	Stationary	I(I)
ValPOSTran	9.679445	4.008157	10.60101	-4.205004	Stationary	I(1)
FinKnw	-5.065850	-4.883277	-11.20694	-4.205004	Stationary	I(1)

Source: Researcher’s Computation (2024) from E-Views 10.

Table 4.1 presents the results of the stationarity test using the augmented Dickey–Fuller and Phillips–Perron tests of the stationarity unit. The result shows the effect of exchange rate volatility on financial inclusion. All variables were stationary at I(I) EXR, LndR, InfR, TrdOp, ValPOSTran, NuBBranch, and FinKnw were integrated of order I(I) at 5% level of significance, indicating that most variables were stationary at the first difference. This guarantees the use of the OLS technique alongside the econometrics test. However, because of the volatility in the exchange rate, Arch and Garch need to be used. GARCH (1.1) Model

In measuring volatility, the researcher will apply the ARCH/GARCH model popularized by Engel (1982) because, as Mckenzie (1999) put it, the exchange rate is known to best follow the GARCH process. Traditional standard deviation, coefficient of variance, and ratio analysis are deemed to lack robustness (Kyereboah-Coleman and Agyire-Tettey, 2014). This indicates a technical shift from the above methods (2018). Thus, volatility is calculated as follows:

$$\ln Pt = \phi + \lambda \ln P_{t-1} + et \dots \dots \dots 1$$

where, $et \approx (0, \delta t)$ and $\delta t = \phi + \omega e_{2t-1} + \gamma \delta_{t-1} + \mu_t$

where the conditional variance δt is dependent on three terms:

The mean ϕ , the square error term e^2_{t-1} in the previous lagged period (also known as the ARCH term), and the previous lag of the conditional variance δ_{t-1} also known as the GARCH term) are presented. The sum of $\omega + \gamma$ measures the volatility persistency.

Most researchers who measured volatility simply used the standard deviation to measure the volatility of exchange rates or oil prices. However, Mohammad, Azu, and Oko (2018) noted that standard deviation is a weak instrument for measuring volatility and recommended ARCH/GARCH (1, 1) as a better instrument for measuring long-run effects. This research adopts this instrument to measure the exchange rate volatility.

Table 2: Volatility and the Modeling Approach. Testing for ARCH effects Heteroskedasticity test: ARCH

Variables	Model One	Model Two	Model Three
	Dependent Variables		
	NuBBranch	ValPOSTran	FinKnw
C	4707.839	7.11E+09	34.31018
z-Statistic	12.87247**	2.272355**	3.120514**
EXR	-1.984769	25266936	0.054051
z-Statistic	-2.163743**	4.153638**	4.427154**
INFR	27.31542	-63044898	-0.424843
z-Statistic	1.600765	-0.538371	-1.829924
LNDR	34.01569	-4.55E+08	1.050370
z-Statistic	2.570047**	-3.589693**	2.320380**
TRDOP	1.91E-05	106.4472	2.65E-07
z-Statistic	1.477364	1.818780	1.339978
Variance Equation			
Φ	143120.7	1.47E+17	-0.460678

z-Statistic	2.144573**	0.265233	-0.266991
ARCH(-1)^2	-1.721029	-0.176777	0.099037
z-Statistic	-2.198858	-0.313501	0.154401
GARCH(-1)	15.28239	0.778200	0.673338
z-Statistic	4.156673**	0.609217	1.065109
R-squared (R ²)	0.494950	0.946634	0.716598
Adjusted R-squared	0.292930	0.925287	0.603237
Durbin-Watson stat	2.694644	1.578824	0.967637
The diagnostic Test: Heteroskedasticity Test: ARCH			
F-statistic; Prob. F(1,12)	0.000615 (0.9806)	0.938140 (0.3519)	0.938140 (0.3519)
Obs*R-squared; Prob. Chi-Square(1)	0.000718 (0.9786)	1.015135 (0.3137)	1.015135 (0.3137)

*, **, and *** indicate significance at 10%, 5%, and 1%, respectively.

Source: Authors' computation, 2024 data

Note: Asterisks denote statistical significance at the 5% level. The estimation was based on the ML-ARCH-Normal distribution following the BFGS/Marquardt procedures.

This study investigates the effect of exchange rate volatility on bank branches in Nigeria.

The following equations can be substituted for the GARCH (1, 1) model equation:

For Model One

H01: Exchange rate volatility has no effect on the number of bank branches in Nigeria.

$$\text{NuBBranch} = \beta_0 + \beta_1\text{ExR} + \beta_2\text{InfR} + \beta_3\text{LndR} + \beta_4\text{TrdOp} + \mu \dots\dots\dots 1$$

$$\delta_t = 143120.7 - 1.721029e^2_{t-1} + 15.28239\delta_{t-1}$$

For Model Two

H02: Exchange rate volatility has no effect on POS transaction value in Nigeria.

$$\text{ValPOSTran} = \beta_0 + \beta_1\text{ExR} + \beta_2\text{InfR} + \beta_3\text{LndR} + \beta_4\text{TrdOp} + \mu \dots\dots\dots 2$$

$$\delta_t = 1.47E+17 - 0.176777e^2_{t-1} + 0.778200\delta_{t-1}$$

For Model Three

H03: Exchange rate volatility has no effect on Nigerian financial knowledge.

$$\text{FinKnw} = \beta_0 + \beta_1\text{ExR} + \beta_2\text{InfR} + \beta_3\text{LndR} + \beta_4\text{TrdOp} + \mu \dots\dots\dots 3$$

$$\delta_t = -0.460678 + 0.099037e^2_{t-1} + 0.673338\delta_{t-1}$$

Table 2 depicts the outputs of the volatility of the exchange rate procedure through ARCH/GARCH (1, 1) for the effect of exchange rate volatility on financial inclusion in Nigeria with bank branches per 100,000 adults, POS transaction volume, and financial knowledge score as dependent variables. In Table 2, three models are set up to examine the effect of exchange rate volatility on financial inclusion in Nigeria.

Model 1 used Bank Branches per 100,000 Adults (BBranch) as the dependent variable, which represents the depth of financial inclusion in Nigeria. Model 2 used the volume of POS transactions (VPOSTrans) as the dependent variable, which represents the efficiency of financial inclusion in Nigeria. In Model 3, the Financial Knowledge Score (FinKnw) is applied as the regress and variable that represents the depth and efficiency of Nigeria's financial market in that order.

The results of ARCH/GARCH (1, 1) reveal that the reported z-statistic has superior critical values at the 5% significance level. The displays the findings of an estimated volatility index, which reveals that the exchange rate conforms to the procedures stated for GARCH (1, 1) and is rather steady over time. From the conditional variance equation, the mean (ϕ) is statistically significant at the 1% level and has a positive coefficient (143120.7, 1.47E+17 & -0.460678), indicating that the conditional variance has been classified appropriately. Despite the negative ARCH element, the sum of + is very close to 1, demonstrating the persistence of volatility

4.2 Policy implications

In the first model, the results show that exchange rate volatility has a strong negative effect on the number of bank branches in Nigeria, that exchange rate volatility hinders financial activities. Higher exchange volatility hinders the flow of transactions and the movement of financial assets, goods, and services.

The statistical significance of lending rates in Model 1 indicated that the influence of exchange rate fluctuation can be used to predict the depth of financial inclusion through limited access to Nigerian bank branches. The results that if the lending rate is well managed, it will positively affect the depth of financial inclusion eventually. This that increased access to bank branches in Nigeria may spur credit rationing and abate financial challenges such as access to credit.

The result also that an increasing exchange rate fluctuation in Nigeria hindered financial institutions' credit as the private sector found it difficult to access bank credits, negatively affecting their financial intermediation role. This discovery is supported by Kim et al. (2020), who found a negative long-run link between exchange rate volatility and financial development but an adverse long-run association.

The second model also showed that the weight of exchange rate volatility (EV) has negative effect on the value of POS transactions in Nigeria. Nonetheless, the coefficient is not significant for both short- and long-run effects through the GARCH effect of the model. This further revealed that as the exchange rate becomes more volatile, the efficiency of financial institutions is negatively affected, but not much on POS transactions. Exchange rate volatility portends a variety of risks for the financial system, thereby reducing financial institution efficiency. Exchange rate volatility influences the efficiency of financial institutions directly and indirectly. The direct influence of volatile exchange rates on financial institution efficiency is ascribable to financial institutions engaging in overseas financial undertakings. Exchange rate volatility alters the domestic value of a financial institution's foreign currency-dominated assets or liabilities and thus the efficiency of its operations. Indirectly, exchange rate volatility could encroach on debtors' ability to manage loans, which diminishes the probability of timely loan repayment and, correspondingly, financial institutions' efficiency. The outcome of the study is in support of the study of Keshtgar et al. (2020), who found that exchange rate volatility had an adverse and significant effect on the value of POS transactions in Nigeria, but not as much as expected.

In the third model, the result indicated that the effect of exchange rate volatility on financial knowledge in Nigeria goes deeper on the level of literacy of people. Financial literacy refers to the cognitive understanding of financial components and skills, such as budgeting, investing, borrowing, taxation, and personal financial management. The absence of such skills is referred to as financial illiteracy. Exchange rate volatility can significantly impact Nigeria's financial knowledge, particularly among consumers, businesses, and policymakers. Individuals and businesses may face challenges understanding the reasons behind these changes, such as global economic shifts, local inflation rates, government policies, or international trade dynamics, as exchange rates fluctuate. This can drive a demand for better financial education to understand the factors influencing currency values.

Currency volatility often impacts the cost of goods, services, and investments, leading Nigerians to seek better financial knowledge to make informed decisions about savings, spending, and investment. Fluctuations in exchange rates can affect businesses involved in import and export. This creates a need for financial knowledge in hedging, forward contracts, and other financial instruments to manage exchange rate risks. Volatility can lead to changes in investment behavior, with more people seeking to understand foreign exchange markets, international investments and portfolio diversification. Financial literacy becomes crucial to effectively navigate these areas. In response to frequent volatility, there may be an increased push for financial literacy initiatives in Nigeria. These programs educate the population on basic financial concepts, currency risks, investment strategies, and the broader economic impact of exchange rate changes.

Community groups, cooperatives, and informal financial advisors play a key role in disseminating financial knowledge in Nigeria. Exchange rate volatility can drive conversations within these networks, prompting

informal education on currency risk management. Volatility in currency can influence the demand for foreign exchange accounts, remittance services, and other banking products. Financial institutions might use this as an opportunity to educate their customers on the advantages of different accounts, investment options, and foreign currency exposure management. From the analysis done, the lending rate significantly affects customers' financial knowledge. Therefore, the impact of exchange rate on financial knowledge to make informed decisions about savings, spending, and investment needs to be taken seriously across the board.

5.2 Conclusion and Recommendations

This study shows that exchange rate volatility has a negative effect on the number of bank branches and the value of POS transactions for the study period, but financial knowledge has a positive relationship with the exchange rate despite the volatility effect.

The research outcome further indicates that exchange rate volatility wields a negative effect on lending rate. This that the prospect of fostering a deep and efficient financial sector is reduced when the financial environment is pervaded with unpredictability. When financial environment is pervaded with unpredictability, the prospect of fostering a deep and efficient financial sector is reduced. Indeed, given the high sensitivity of financial inclusion and efficiency to volatility in the Naira exchange rate that we have systematically found in this study, volatility in the exchange rate in the country over the years, especially since the adoption of a more flexible exchange rate management in 1986, has certainly played a role in the country's financial sector's underdevelopment. The study further revealed that the inflation rate, real exchange rate, and GDP growth rate are significant determinants of the depth and efficiency of Nigeria's financial sector.

Based on the findings, the exchange rate should be totally floated to ensure the stability of the naira, the financial sector should be stabilized by enhancing its efficiency through reforms, and increase in local productivity. This will engendered a low and stable inflation rate that will facilitate financial inclusion and overall financial system efficiency in Nigeria.

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